

The Effect of Bambara groundnut diet on the proximate composition of the slime of *Archachatina marginata*.

Emmanuel E. Odiaka¹ & Bernadette Ejidike²

¹Department of Ecotourism and Wildlife Management, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Ecotourism and Wildlife Management, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Emmanuel Odiaka, E-mail: emmanuele.odiaka@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The research work was carried out for 60 days on the Effect of Bambara groundnut diet on the proximate composition of the slime of *Archachatina marginata*. One hundred and eighty *Archachatina marginata* snails of approximately equal body weight were used for this study. The snails were randomly divided into 12 experimental groups of 15 snails each, assigned to 4 dietary treatments that were replicated 3 times giving a total of 45 snails per treatment. Results showed that *Archachatina marginata* snails fed 45% Bambara groundnut diet had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher Feed Intake than those fed lower BGN dietary levels. The final body weight (170.15g), and weight gain (15.01g) of snails fed 45% BGN levels were also significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than values obtained from 0%, 15%, and 30% BGN dietary protein levels. The result also revealed that dietary crude protein of (24.93%) at 45% BGN level resulted in higher slime crude protein (14.18%) level while the lowest slime crude protein levels were recorded at 0% BGN dietary levels. This showed that feeding can affect the proximate composition of snail slime. The inclusion of BGN dietary levels at 45% should be considered as the most appropriate since the important parameters that impacted the slime proximate composition of the experimental snails was recorded at this level. *Archachatina marginata* fed 45% BGN dietary level produced proportionately more slime.

KEYWORDS

Snail, Slime, Bambara Groundnut, Performance, Proximate Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Snails have successfully established their presence in both the terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem. The growth of snail like other animals differs with respect to what they are fed. The nutrient content of the feed has a strong and positive impact on the growth of snails. (Ogunyemi, 2019). The fact that snails are feeding on all experimental diets with weight gains is an indication of the acceptance of

the Bambara groundnut diet by the snails. This is despite the fact the diets differ in capacity. The quality and level of nutrient in the diet is important for animal production. (Anigbogu *et al*, 2011).

The origin of Bambara groundnut is linked to the Bambara people in the Timbuktu tribe of central Mali. The crop belongs to the family Leguminosae and sub family Papilionoideae. (Hillocks *et al*, 2012). Studies by Alikwe *et al* (2014) has shown snail as a major source of protein and rich in amino acid. Nutrient deficiencies can lead to the compromising of physiological process. (Gernand *et al*, 2016).

The major food of snails are leafy vegetables, household and industrial waste. They derive majority of their nutrients from plant materials. Plants and plant products are major sources of nutrient for snails. However, snails fed on a combination of feeds have done better in terms of growth and reproductive performance. (Akintomide,2004).

Snails produce mucus which are slimy in nature and they help snails in movements, lubricating their paths. Apart from helping the snail in movement, slimes protect the snails from injuries and moisture loss during extreme weather conditions (Jeff *et al*, 2017) Snail slime can be very good ingredient for the preparation of industrial, food and medicinal products. Medications for diabetes and ulcer have also been prepared from snail slime. (Gugu *et al*, 2020)

The study will highlight the proximate analysis of the slime of *Archachatina marginata* that demonstrates its potential as a food and medicinal ingredient.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Site

The study area was at the wildlife domestication unit of The Department of Ecotourism and Wildlife Management of The Federal University of Technology, Akure, situated in Ondo State, in the South West region of Nigeria. Ondo state lies on latitude 05.⁰ 41' N and longitude 06⁰ 32' E. The area lies within the tropical rainforest belt with annual rainfall of about 1,613 mm per year and an annual mean temperature of about 27°C. The dry season usually occurs between October and March while the raining season starts from April to October.

Experimental Snails

One hundred and eighty *Archachatina marginata* snails of equal body weight were randomly assigned to four dietary Bambara groundnut waste treatments containing 0%, 15%, 30% and 45% protein inclusion levels respectively.

Feed Ingredients and their Sources

The experimental feed ingredient was Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*) Other feed ingredients included in the experimental diets were maize, wheat offal, fish meal, bone meal,

Received: 28 February 2025

Revised: 7 March 2025

Accepted: 12 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15009708](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15009708)

limestone, oil, groundnut cake and vitamin premix. The ingredients were all purchased from Farm Support, Akure.

Experimental Diet

Bambara groundnut meal was used as the main protein source to formulate four Bambara groundnut diets containing 0%, 15%, 30% and 45% protein inclusion levels respectively.

Experimental Procedure

For this experiment, one hundred and eighty juvenile snails were used. The snails were divided into 4 groups of equal body weight and 15 snails each in a group. The snails were randomly selected. The snails were housed in plastic baskets labeled as box A for dietary treatment at 0% Bambara groundnut waste inclusion level (Control Experiment), box B at 15% Bambara groundnut waste inclusion level, box C for 30% Bambara groundnut waste inclusion level and box D for 45% Bambara groundnut waste inclusion level. Each plastic basket had 15 snails and each treatment was replicated three times.

Management of the Experimental Snails

Twelve plastic baskets were used for the experiment. Before introducing the snails, the plastic baskets were filled with sterilized garden soil up to 8 cm high. Random samplings were used to introduce the snails into the baskets. Feeding of the snails was *ad libitum* for a period of 60 days. Feed intake was determined daily by the weigh back technique. Water was also given *ad libitum* for the same 60 days. The snails were weighed at the beginning of the experiment, subsequently once in every week and at the end of the experiment. All measurements were taken between 7:00am and 10:00am and mortality records were kept on a daily basis.

Sampling and Sampling Procedure

Simple random sampling was used to introduce the snails for the study into the basket. The feed and the water were served inside flat trays. At the end of the experiment, 8 snails from each treatment were selected and slaughtered for proximate analysis according to AOAC (2010).

Chemical Analysis

Proximate compositions:

The proximate composition of the experimental diet was determined according to the standard methods (AOAC, 2010). Determinations were done in triplicates for each analysis.

Table 1: Percentage Composition of the experimental diets

Ingredients	0%	15%	30%	45%
BGM	-	3.5	7.0	10.0
GNC	12.00	10.00	8.40	6.60
Fish Meal	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00
Maize	47	47	47	47
Wheat offal	6.00	4.50	2.60	1.40
Bone Meal	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Limestone	5	5	5	5
Vitamin premix	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Palm oil	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Total (%)	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Extraction of The Snail Slime

A method used described by Adikwu and Nnamani (2005) with little modifications was used. A total of twenty *Archachatina marginata* snails comprising five snails from each treatment were selected, washed for Sime. The slime was scraped from the snails using a spatula into a bowl of water, filtered and precipitated using chilled acetone. Freeze drying of the precipitate was carried out at -40°C until a greyish brown flake was obtained which was then pulverized into fine form and stored in the refrigerator for analysis.

Chemical Analysis and Determinations

The sample analysis was carried out on dry matter basis. The diet samples were analysed for crude protein ether extract, crude fibre, ash, moisture and nitrogen free extract. The slime samples were analysed for Moisture Content, crude fat, crude protein, ash content, and carbohydrate content.

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were analysed statistically using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SPSS 15.0. The significance difference among mean was determined by the use of Duncan,s Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1995)

RESULTS

Table 2: Proximate composition of the experimental diets

Ingredients	Diet 1(0%)	Diet 2(15%)	Diet 3(30%)	Diet 4(45%)
Dry Matter	95.12 ^a	94.89 ^a	94.95 ^a	94.68 ^a
Crude Protein (%)	24.11 ^b	24.11 ^b	24.39 ^b	24.93 ^b
Ether Extract (%)	2.73 ^a	3.45 ^a	3.70 ^c	3.60 ^c
Crude Fibre (%)	9.30 ^c	9.05 ^b	8.79 ^a	8.79 ^a
Ash (%)	8.89 ^b	9.92 ^a	9.67 ^a	9.61 ^a
Moisture	4.88 ^c	5.11 ^b	5.05 ^b	5.32 ^a
Nitrogen FreeExtract (NFE)	50.09 ^a	48.36 ^b	48.40 ^b	42.43 ^b

Value with different superscripts along the same column are significantly (P<0.05) different.

Table 3: Growth Performance of *Archachatina marginata* fed varying inclusion level of BGM supplements

Performance Variables	Diet1(0%)	Diet2(15%)	Diet3(30%)	Diet4(45%)	SEM
Initial Weight of Snails (g)	141.22±0.35 ^a	142.74±0.76 ^a	142.14±0.00 ^a	143.91±0.75 ^a	0.56
Final Weight of Snails (g)	144.31±0.24 ^b	145.74±0.21 ^b	150.50±0.00 ^{ab}	157.12±0.18 ^a	3.13
Feed Intake (g)	57.36±1.64 ^{ab}	56.51±2.00 ^{ab}	60.57±1.06 ^a	93.53±0.35 ^a	8.89
Weight gain/snail (g)	3.09±0.27 ^b	3.17±0.00 ^b	8.36±0.39 ^{ab}	13.21±0.09 ^a	2.72
Av. Shell length (cm)	8.49±0.01 ^b	8.41±0.01 ^b	8.84±0.96 ^c	8.93±0.17 ^a	0.18
Av. Shell width (cm)	3.28±0.01 ^b	3.97±0.96 ^b	4.02±0.01 ^b	4.85±0.01 ^a	0.08
Av. Shell weight (g)	1.37	1.52	1.51	1.74	0.09
Feed Conversion Ratio	11.76±0.46 ^a	15.65±0.93 ^{ab}	7.86±0.52 ^b	7.91±0.74 ^b	2.98

Data represents mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates. Means with different superscripts a, b, c within the same rows are significantly different ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4 Proximate composition of the slime fed the experimental diets

Feed ingredients	Diet 1 (0%)	Diet 2 (15%)	Diet 3 (30%)	Diet 4 (45%)
Moisture	91.02 \pm 0.00 ^a	84.80 \pm 0.00 ^a	82.35 \pm 0.29 ^a	82.30 \pm 0.29 ^a
Crude Protein (%)	6.54 \pm 0.02 ^c	12.57 \pm 0.03 ^{ab}	13.63 \pm 0.09 ^{ab}	14.18 \pm 0.00 ^c
Crude fat (%)	0.08 \pm 0.13 ^a	0.08 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.01 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.03 \pm 0.13 ^a
Crude Fibre(%)	ND	ND	ND	ND
Ash(%)	1.03 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.03 \pm 0.03 ^a	1.05 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.08 \pm 0.00 ^a
Dry matter	4.98 \pm 0.00 ^a	4.81 \pm 0.00 ^a	4.80 \pm 0.00 ^a	4.80 \pm 0.01
Carbohydrate (NFE)	1.33 \pm 0.29 ^a	1.52 \pm 0.37 ^a	1.96 \pm 0.15 ^a	1.41 \pm 1.59 ^a

Data represents mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates. Value with different superscripts along the same column are significantly ($P > 0.05$) different.

DISCUSSION

Discussion

In Table 2, snails fed 45% BGN diet had the highest crude protein content (29.93%) while the crude protein content of 0% and 15% BGN levels were the lowest. There was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference in the Nitrogen Free Extract (NFE) of 15%, 30% and 45% BGN dietary levels. In table 3, snails fed 45% BGN levels had significant ($P < 0.05$) Feed Intake than those fed 15% BGN levels. The Final Body Weight value (170.15g) and Weight Gain value (15.01g) of snails fed 45% BGN diets were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than values obtained from snails fed 0%, 15%, and 30% BGN diets. The Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) values of snails fed 30%, and 45% diets (6.29 and 6.23) were comparable ($P > 0.05$) and significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from the FCR value (18.65) of snails fed with 15% BGN diets. There were significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among treatments in final body weight and weight gain (WG). The result is in agreement with the findings of Ogunyemi (2021) and Akinnusi (2004). The final body weight and mean gain of snails were improved ($P < 0.05$) as the dietary protein level increased to 45%. This agrees with the earlier report

of Ewuola *et al.* (2015), who found that the weight gain of grower rabbits was improved significantly ($P < 0.05$) as the dietary protein level increased.

Snails fed 45% BGN diets had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher shell length and width values (9.93cm and 5.15cm) respectively than those fed 0%, 15% and 30% BGN diet (Table 3) Shell size is significantly related to slime production, with larger shells producing more slimes. Larger shell size means that the snail have higher growth rate signifying higher Slime production. Larger snails produce more slime than smaller snails. Below the 45% dietary protein level, there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) improvement on growth performance and this can result in lower slime production. This shows that the performance and slime production of growing land snail will not be optimized when they are offered 0% and 15% protein level diet. Growth rate is positively correlated with slime production. Earlier studies have recommended contrasting protein levels for growth of snails ranging between 19.5 to 26%. (Tchowan *et al.*, 2018). Ejidike (2001) reported that diets containing 20% to 25% CP had positive influence on the growth performance of *Archachatina marginata*.

The final body weight and mean weight gain of snails at 45% were at variance with the value (18%CP) reported for growing snail (*Archachatina marginata*) by Torhemen *et al.* (2020). However, protein dietary level of 24.28% has been used by Adeyemo and Akeredolu (2002). The snail fed with 30% and 45% Bambara groundnut waste diet had weight gain values of 9.63g and 15.01g respectively. This signifies that both protein level diets were highly utilized and converted to snail flesh. This corroborates with the statement of Cobbinah *et al.* (2008) affirming that the growth performance of snail largely depends on the availability of adequate nutrition and good soil lack of which may cause fragile shell.

Table 4 showed the proximate composition of the snail slime fed the varying protein levels of the Bambara groundnut experimental diet. Dietary crude protein of (24.93%) resulted in higher slime crude protein of 14.18%. while the lowest slime crude protein content (6.54%) was recorded at 0% Bambara groundnut inclusion level. Increased protein intake enhances slime production in snails slime. This agrees with the result produced by Oyedele *et al.* (2020). The result also agrees with the findings of Ademolu *et al.* (2019) that optimal slime production range of 30-35% supports maximum slime production. Higher protein content also increases slime viscosity (Oyedele *et al.*, 2020) while glycoprotein levels in slime, positively correlate with protein intake (Souza *et al.*, 2018) The significant increase in protein content of the slime with dietary protein content highlights the ability to manipulate snail slime composition through dietary interventions. The highest crude fat content was recorded at 45% dietary level while the highest ash content was obtained at 0% Bambara groundnut dietary level. However, there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference observed in crude fat content of snail slime as dietary fat increases, The result is at variance with crude fat content of

4.82% reported by Nwosu *et al* (2019). It is of note that crude fat percentage may vary depending on snail species, diet and environmental conditions.

Table 4 also showed that the snail slime has 91.02 % moisture content for 0% Bambara groundnut dietary protein levels, 84.80% for 15% dietary protein levels, 82.35 % for 30% dietary protein level and 82.30% for 45% dietary protein levels. Moisture helps maintain hydration and slime consistency. The moisture content of the snail slime obtained from the four dietary treatments fall within the range of 73.67 – 99.20 that has been reported on snail meat by Enaji *et al* (2008).

The ash content was 1.03% for 0% dietary protein level, 1.03% for 15% protein level 1.05 % for 30% and 1.08 % for 45% Bambara groundnut dietary protein levels respectively. This is an indication of rich mineral content possessed by the slime.

The crude fat content of the snail slime was 0.08% for diet D1, 0.08 % for diet D2, 1.01 % for diet D3 and 1.03% for diet D4. While the crude protein content was 6.54% for diet D1, 12.57% for diet D2, 13.63% for diet D3 and 14.18% for diet D4. The result showed that slime has high percentage crude protein content. Dietary Protein encourages slime production and overall health of snails. This is in agreement with reports of Eruvbetine (2012), and Okon & Ibom (2012) that snail is a high-quality food that is rich in protein.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

The result obtained in the study shows that up to 15%, 30% and 45% BGN inclusion level in the diet of snails can improve the quality of snail, slime. The inclusion of BGN source at 45% should be considered as the most appropriate since the most important growth parameters of Weight Gain, Feed Conversion Rate, Shell Length and Width increased at that level. This resulted in increase in the proximate parameters of the snail slime. Snails fed 45% BGN dietary level produced proportionately more slime.

The study demonstrates that *A. marginata* snail slime possesses promising resources with protein that are high as protein content of its diet increases.

The ingredient (Bambara groundnut) belongs to the group of “underutilized plants” for animal nutrition. The result of the study will elevate the status of this plant as a rich source of protein for animal feed.

REFERENCES

- Ademolu, K. G., Oyedele, A. O. (2019). Influence of Stocking Density on Growth and Slime Production in Snails (*Archachatina marginata*). *Journal of Animal Science and Technology*, 61(3), 247-256.
- Adeyemo, A. I., Akerodolu, K. E. (2002). Performance of the African Giant Snail (*Archachatina marginata*) on different feed items. Proc. 27th Ann. Conf. Nig. Soc. Of Animal prod. (NSAP) March 12-21, 2002. Fed. Univ. of Tech. Akure, Nigeria. Pp: 338-339.
- Akinnusi, O. (2004) Introduction to snail farming (2nd Edition), Abeokuta, Triolas Esquisite Ventures, pp 42-44.
- Alikwe, P. C. N., Yeigba, J, Akinnusi, B., Oyenike, F. A., Ohimein E. J. (2014) Performance and Carcass Characteristics of Giant African land Snails fed *Alchorrea cordifolia* leaf meal in replacement of soybean meal, *International Journal of Research in Agriculture and Food Science*, 1(6):2311-2476.
- Anigbogu, N. M., Onyejekwe, I. E., Ndukwe C. O., (2011) Metabolism of protein and energy by Maradi goats fed *Zymomonas mobilis* fed degraded rice hull diets. *Proceedings of the 16th annual conference of the Animal Science of Nigeria*, Kogi State University, Faculty of Agriculture, Anyigba, Kogi State. Pp 99-103.
- AOAC, (Association of Official Analytical Chemist (2010) Official Methods of Analysis. 18th Edition. Horwitz, W. (Ed) Washington D C.
- Cobbinah, J. R., Vink, A. and Onwuka, B, (2008) Snail farming: production, processing and marketing *1st Edition*. Wageningen: Agromisa CTA. 78p
- Duncan, D. E. (1955), Multiple Range and Multiple F test. *A Biometric Approach*, 11: 1-42
- Ejidike, B.N. (2001). Comparative Effect of Supplemental and Complete diets on the performance of African Giant Land Snail (*Archachatina marginata*). Proc. 26th Ann. Conf. Nig. Soc. For Anim. Prod. (NSAP) March 18-22, 2001. NAPRI, Zaria, Nigeria. 151-153
- Ejidike, B. N., and Afolayan, T. A., (2010) Effects of natural and compounded ration on growth

performance of African Giant Land Snail (*Archachatina marginata*). *Journal of Resaerch in Forestry, Wildlife and Environment*, 2(1):107-111

Eneji, C. A., Ogogo, A. U., Emmanuel-Ikpeme, C. A. and Okon, O. E. Nutritional Assessment of Some Nigerian Land and Water Snail Species. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 2008, 1(2): 56-60.

Eruvbetine, D. Nutrition and feeding strategies of the giant African land snails. Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Giant African Land Snail. February, Abeokuta, Nigeria, 2012; 12 – 15: 8 – 18.

Ewuola, G. O., Ibronke, S. I. and Fashakin, J. B. (2015) Formlation and Nutritional Evaluation of Maize, Bambara groundnut and Cowpea seeds blend complementary foods. *Am. J. Food and Nutr.* 3(4):101-105.

Gernand, A. D., Schulze, K. J., Stewart, C. P., West, K. P. Jr, and Christain, P. (2016) Micronitrient deficiency in pregnancy worldwide: health effect and prevention, *Nature reviews. Endocrinology*, 12(5): 274-289.

Hillocks, R. J., Benneth, C., Mponda, O. M (2012). Bambara nut: A Review of Utilization, Market Potential and Crop Improvement. *African crop science journal* 20: 1-6.

Nwosu, C. C., & Ogbu, C. C. (2019). Physicochemical and Nutritional Properties of Snail Slime from *Helix aspersa*. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 19(7): 1755-1764.

Ogunyemi O. O. (2019). Growth performance of juvenile African Giant Land Snail (*Archachatina marginata*) fed on different natural plant foods. Proceeding of 3rd Annual Conference of Wildlife Society of Nigeria, Ibadan, Nigeria pp 62-83.

Ogunyemi, O. O. (2021). Growth performance of African Giant Land Snail *Archachatina marginata* fed varying dietary protein levels of plant source. *OJ Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 3(3): 555-616

Okon, B. and Ibom, L. A. Snail Breeding and Snailery Management. Calabar: Freshdew Production, 2012; 80.

Oyeagu, C. E., Udeh, F. U., Uzochukwu, I. E., Osita, C. O., Ugwu, S. O., and Agugom, O. H., (2018) Effect of dietary *Centrosima pubescen* leaf meal on growth and reproduction traits of *Archachatina marginata* snails. *Journal of Applied Animal Resaerch*, 46(1):947-952.

- Oyedele, A. O., Odukoya, O. O., & Ademolu, J. A. (2020). Effects of Dietary Protein Levels on Growth and Slime Production in *Archachatina marginata*. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 36(2): 1-9.
- Souza, P. M., & Freitas, J. C. (2018). Nutritional Evaluation of Snail Feed Supplements on Growth and Slime Production in *Helix aspersa*. *Journal of Molluscan Research*, 43(2): 147-155.
- Tchowan, G. M, Ngoula, F, Kenfack, A, Tchoumbooue, J, (2018) Effects of protein levels on the performance of the Giant African Land Snail in captivity. *Journal of Agricultural Science* 10(4): 278-286.